

Understanding Trends in Public Relations Research in Asia (2013-2022): A Bibliometric Analysis with VOS and R Package

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Received: 22nd Oct 2025 / Accepted : 29th Oct 2025 ,

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Abstract

The strategic communication process between an organisation or individual and their target audience with the goal of building and maintaining positive relationships and managing perceptions is referred to as public relations. Recent years have seen an enormous amount of literature in the area of public relations due to the growing interest of academicians and practitioners in the subject. Using the R package bibliometrix and the Visualisation of Similarities

(VOS) viewer programme, this study aims to enhance a graphical mapping of the bibliographic data for public relations publications in select countries of Asia. The study showed that there is an increase in publications related to public relations with a fluctuating tendency. The results also revealed that the USA, China, and South Korea are the top three countries for publishing articles on public relations. The network view map generated using the VoS viewer and R software indicated that studies on

public relations were roughly divided into three major clusters and a few very smaller clusters.

Keywords: Public relations, Visualisation of Similarities, R Package, Asia, Bibliometric analysis

1. Introduction

Public Relations is a multifaceted discipline that involves managing an organisation's communication and relationships with its stakeholders. It seeks to improve the organisation's image and reputation among the general public, the media, employees, investors, customers, and other interested parties. Public relations is a strategic communication process that allows organisations to build and maintain trust and credibility with their stakeholders, which is critical for long-term success. Public relations is an essential component of any organisation's overall communication strategy. Public relations is a distinct management function that assists in the establishment and maintenance of mutual lines of communication, understanding, acceptance, and cooperation between an organisation and its public; involves the management of problems or issues; assists management in staying informed about and responsive to public opinion; defines and emphasises management's responsibility to serve the public interest; and assists management in staying abreast of and effectively utilising change (Rex,1976). Public relations is the management function that evaluates public attitudes, identifies an individual's or an organisation's policies and procedures that are in the public interest, and plans and executes a plan of action to gain public understanding and acceptance (John,1963).

Another important aspect of public relations is internal communication. Internal communication that is effective assists in aligning employee values with organisational values, fostering a positive workplace culture, and improving employee engagement and satisfaction. Internal communication strategies are developed and implemented by public relations professionals to inform and engage employees,

promote a positive workplace culture, and foster a sense of community within the organisation.

Social media has grown in importance as a tool for public relations professionals to reach and engage with their target audience. Social media platforms enable public relations professionals to share information, build relationships, and solicit feedback from stakeholders. Social media is frequently used by public relations professionals to share news and updates, respond to comments and inquiries, and create and participate in online communities.

With ever-expanding scope and importance, it is important to study the pattern of research work in public relations in Asia for several reasons. Because of the continent's diverse cultural context, studying the pattern of research work in public relations in Asia is critical. Understanding the research patterns in public relations can help identify effective communication strategies that are culturally relevant and sensitive, given Asia's rich cultural heritage and varying cultural norms, values, and communication styles across different countries. Researchers and practitioners can gain insights into the unique challenges and opportunities of conducting public relations activities in the region by studying research work in Asia and developing strategies that are tailored to local contexts. The analysis and insights derived from the study can be useful for corporates, multinational corporations, governments and other institutions that intend to make their public relations campaigns in Asia successful one. This will also add to the existing literature in the lexicon of public relations in the region.

In addition, making sense of the research trends and patterns in the field of public relations will supplement and complement various business operations of companies and agencies that have bases in Asia. With multifaceted markets and business avenues, Asia is spontaneously enhancing its domain in the economic sphere. This allows organisations and institutions to adapt and navigate complex communication landscapes and cultivate relationships with diverse stakeholders including a variety of

customers and consumers. Businesses can gain insights into the best practices, trends, and strategies for effective communication in the region by studying research patterns in public relations in Asia. This understanding assists organisations in understanding the unique challenges and opportunities associated with conducting public relations activities in Asia, such as managing reputation in diverse markets, addressing cultural sensitivities, and building trust with local stakeholders. It enables businesses to tailor their communication strategies based on research findings, which can significantly improve communication effectiveness and, ultimately, success in Asian markets.

The authors chose bibliometric analysis as this is the best method to conduct a quantitative study of public relations-related publications in select Asian countries. Bibliometrics is a branch of library and information science (LIS) that employs a variety of techniques and methods to quantitatively evaluate research articles and other scholarly documents. To analyse, process, and prepare significant concepts, bibliometric procedures rely on information technology. The word bibliometrics was coined by Pritchard (1969), who defined it as follows: "To shed light on the process of written communication and of the nature and course of a discipline (in so far as this is displayed through written communication), by means of counting and analysing the various facets of written communication (Pritchard,1969)."The bibliometric analysis employs a systematic, explicit, and uniform evaluation procedure to report research contributions in a subject domain.

This study serves as a reference for any researcher with an interest in the field of public relations and provides an up-to-date summary of the research literature to promote a better grasp of the principles of public relations. The methodology used in the current study gives the researchers insights into the patterns and trends in scholarly publications on public relations originating in Asia. By analysing the frequency and distribution of keywords, authors, institutions, and citation patterns, researchers can

gain a better understanding of the key topics and themes under public relations. Bibliometric analysis can also help researchers to identify the most influential authors, institutions, and publications in public relations. This can be useful in identifying potential collaborators, mentors, and sources of funding for research projects. Bibliometric analysis can help researchers to evaluate the impact of their own publications and research output in the domain of public relations. By analysing citation patterns and co-authorship networks, researchers can gain insights into the visibility and influence of their research. Bibliometric analysis can also help researchers to identify research gaps and areas of potential future research in the field of public relations. By identifying areas of low publication output or areas where there is a high concentration of research, researchers can gain insights into where there may be opportunities for new research and innovation. This study provides the data analysis of the research literature on public relations from the chosen Asian nations by utilising the R package bibliometrix and the Visualisation of Similarities (VOS) viewer tool.

2. Methodology

Bibliometric analysis was used in this study to review the public relations literature by utilising the R package bibliometrix and the Visualisation of Similarities (VOS) viewer tool. The methodology of this study involved several steps. The first step was data collection, where the Scopus database was selected, and relevant search terms were used to identify publications in the field of public relations. The next step was data screening, where the publications were screened to ensure that they met the inclusion criteria for the study. The third step was data analysis, where bibliometric techniques are used to analyse the collected data. This included analysing citation patterns, identifying influential authors and publications, identifying research trends in the field etc. Finally, the results of the analysis were interpreted and reported, providing insights into the state of research in public relations and highlighting future research directions.

2.1 Data Collection and search strategy

Scopus database is used in order to carry out the study. The most important reason to select the Scopus database is that it is Elsevier's abstract and citation database, which was introduced in 2004. It comprises almost 36,377 titles from around 11,678 publishers (22,794 active titles and 13,583 inactive titles), of which 34,346 are peer-reviewed journals in the top-level subject areas of biological sciences, social sciences, physical sciences, and health sciences (Elsevier, n.d.). It encompasses three different sources: trade journals, book series, and journals. Hence the Scopus database is used for extracting the data to carry out the study. After thorough investigation, the following search strings were used for the title, abstract, and keywords to find out the documents connected to public relations: (TITLE-ABS-KEY (public AND relations) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("public relations") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (publicrelations)). The search carried out in the Scopus database produced 23,112 documents. The data for the study was retrieved on 27 March 2023 from the Scopus database. The next step was to limit the study to 10 years from 2013-2022. After this step, the number of documents was confined to 9,007. In the subject area, social science, Business Management and Accounting, Arts and Humanities and multidisciplinary were selected. After this limitation, the number of documents came down to 6,543. Further, the search was narrowed down to the specific document type. Articles were selected leaving all other types of documents and the search result has been reduced to 6,543. In the next step, the search was further limited to only final documents leaving the documents which are yet to be published. After that, the search results showed 6,455 documents. The documents on public relations are published in many languages. Since the English language is the most popular and mostly used for

research, hence, for the study only articles published in the English language were included. After that, the number of articles then came down to 6075. Since the study is confined to the countries belonging to the Asia continent, we selected only the countries belonging to Asia continents with a minimum of 10 publications in the public relations field. Finally, the search results showed 1013 documents. The final set of articles was retrieved from the Scopus database, and analysis were carried out using VoS and R software. An approach similar to that recommended by Cancino et al. (2019) and Colares et al. (2020) was utilised to analyse the obtained data using the VOSviewer. Additionally, bibliometrix analysis has been applied to this study using the R package, as suggested by Luo et al. (2018) and Anglada-Tort and Sanfilippo (2019).

3. Data analysis and visualisation

1013 distinct articles on the defined topic were included in the Scopus dataset, with a total of 2776 authors. The authors have used 3312 different keywords to categorise their investigations using an overview of the dataset. Additionally, there were 11.37 citations on average for each work. This finding suggests that while many articles exist with few citations, few articles have a huge number of them. The dataset also contained 187 articles on public relations that were solely written by a single author, while 843 were multi-authored articles. The average number of co-authors per manuscript was 3.23, which shows that attempts at collaborative study frequently result in public relations. The statistics of this data are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Summary of the bibliographic statistics for Public Relations articles

Description	Results
Articles	1013
Period	2013 - 2022
Author's Keywords (DE)	3312
Keywords Plus (ID)	2667
Sources (Journals, Books, etc)	412
Authors	2776
Authors of multi-authored articles	843
Authors of single-authored docs	170
Single-authored articles	187
Average citations per articles	11.37
Co-Authors per Doc	3.23
International co-authorships %	28.92

Fig. 1 Annual scientific production of public relations-related articles indexed in SCOPUS, 2013–2022

Public relations publications from 2013 to 2022 are distributed across the board in Fig. 1. As shown in Fig.1, the growth in public relations publications is fluctuating, but it shows an increased growth. The year 2019 has the highest number of publications in the field with 134 articles, followed by 121 articles in 2022 and 120 articles in 2020. The findings, as shown in this table, demonstrate the rising interest that academics have each year in the discipline of public relations.

Fig. 2 The top publishing countries in the public relations

According to the total number of publications counted for each author’s country, the productive nations are shown in Fig. 2. In terms of publishing articles on public relations, the United States leads a group of 64 nations, followed by China, South Korea, India and Japan. Public Relations Agencies from China are listed among the top 250 PR agencies globally with BlueFocus among the Global top 9 places (Top 250, 2021). The analysis also shows that other Asian nations like South Korea, Japan, Singapore, Hong Kong, and Malaysia have made efforts to advance research in the field of public relations.

Table 2

The top 20 most-cited articles

Sl. No.	Authors	Title	Year	Global Citation	TC/Year	Local citation
1	Eric W.K. See-To, Kevin K.W. Ho	Value co-creation and purchase intention in social network sites: The role of electronic Word-of-Mouth and trust - A theoretical analysis	2014	362	36.2	0
2	Lee D., Moon J., Kim Y.J., Yi M.Y.	Antecedents and consequences of mobile phone usability: Linking simplicity and interactivity to satisfaction, trust, and brand loyalty	2015	248	27.56	0
3	Ainin S., Parveen F., Moghavvemi S., Jaafar N.I., Shuib N.L.M.	Factors influencing the use of social media by SMEs and its performance outcomes	2015	227	25.22	1
4	Kang M., Sung M.	How symmetrical employee communication leads to employee engagement and positive employee communication behaviours: The mediation of employee-organisation relationships	2017	153	21.86	3
5	Kumar B.S., Ravi V.	A survey of the applications of text mining in financial domain	2016	150	18.75	1
6	Feng F., He X., Wang X., Luo C., Liu Y., Chua T.-S.	Temporal relational ranking for stock prediction	2019	149	29.8	0

7	Zhu Q., Feng Y., Choi S.-B.	The role of customer relational governance in environmental and economic performance improvement through green supply chain management	2017	141	20.14	0
8	Tajudeen F.P., Jaafar N.I., Ainin S.	Understanding the impact of social media usage among organisations	2018	137	22.83	1
9	Ahani A., Rahim N.Z.A., Nilashi M.	Forecasting social CRM adoption in SMEs: A combined SEM-neural network method	2017	123	17.57	0
10	Liaw S.Y., Zhou W.T., Lau T.C., Siau C., Chan S.W.C.	An interprofessional communication training using simulation to enhance safe care for a deteriorating patient	2014	121	12.1	4
11	Dhanesh G.S., Duthler G.	Relationship management through social media influencers: Effects of followers' awareness of paid endorsement	2019	118	23.6	4
12	Luo X., Kanuri V.K., Andrews M.	How does CEO tenure matter? the mediating role of firm-employee and firm-customer relationships	2014	107	10.7	4
13	Hong H.	Government websites and social media's influence on government-public relationships	2013	107	9.73	0
14	Lee S.T., Basnyat I.	From Press Release to News: Mapping the Framing of the 2009 H1N1 A Influenza Pandemic	2013	95	8.64	2

15	Yen Y.-S., Wu F.-S.	Predicting the adoption of mobile financial services: The impacts of perceived mobility and personal habit	2016	93	11.63	0
16	Liau B.Y., Tan P.P.	Gaining customer knowledge in low cost airlines through text mining	2014	91	9.1	0
17	Jafari Navimipour N., Soltani Z.	The impact of cost, technology acceptance and employees' satisfaction on the effectiveness of the electronic customer relationship management systems	2016	89	11.13	9
18	Yang S.-U., Kang M., Cha H.	A study on dialogic communication, trust, and distrust: Testing a scale for measuring organization–public dialogic communication (OPDC)	2015	89	9.89	1
19	Himmelboim I., Golan G.J., Moon B.B., Suto R.J.	A Social Networks Approach to Public Relations on Twitter: Social Mediators and Mediated Public Relations	2014	80	8	6
20	Chuang S.-H., Lin H.-N.	The roles of infrastructure capability and customer orientation in enhancing customer-information quality in CRM systems: Empirical evidence from Taiwan	2013	79	7.18	7

The citation analysis was used in this bibliometric study to examine the level of connectedness between pairs of nodes (articles) in the 1013-node network. The top 20 publications in Table 2 are ordered by the number of local citations. The term “local citation” refers to how many times an article has been referenced by other articles in the 1013-node network (Niknejad et al., 2021). The term “global citation”, in contrast, refers to all of the citations that the work has received on Scopus (Niknejad et al., 2021). A substantial difference between the global citations and

Table 3

The top 10 most local-cited journals from the reference lists

Sl. No.	Journal Name	ARTICLES
1.	PUBLIC RELATIONS REVIEW	101
2.	BMC MEDICAL EDUCATION	44
3.	NURSE EDUCATION TODAY	24
4.	PLOS ONE	22
5.	JOURNAL OF COMMUNICATION MANAGEMENT	16
6.	JOURNAL OF PUBLIC RELATIONS RESEARCH	15
7.	JURNAL KOMUNIKASI: MALAYSIAN JOURNAL OF COMMUNICATION	15
8.	MEDICAL TEACHER	12
9.	CORPORATE COMMUNICATIONS	11
10.	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH	11

Table 3 presents the data of the top 10 most local-cited journals from the reference lists. The first journal, i.e. Public Relations Review matches with the journals' co-citation for public relations as shown

in Fig. 3. However, the order of the topmost local-cited journals (Table 3) and the journals' co-citation for public relations (Fig. 3) does not match. The data from the top 10 locally referenced

journals from the reference lists are shown in Table 3. Public Relations Review, the first journal, fits the publications' co-citations for public relations, as seen in Fig. 3. The order of the top local-cited journals (Table 3) and the co-citations of the journals for public relations (Fig. 3), however, is not in order.

Fig. 4 Co-citation of authors for publications of public relations

In the area of public relations study in Asia, Fig. 4 shows the co-citation of writers. Wang, Y. is one of the most mentioned authors in the field of public relations because his publication is the most referenced piece in the research on the subject. Zhang, Y come in second place followed by Wang, X for most co-citations. In Fig. 4, the various clusters and their connections are depicted by means of varied colours.

Fig. 5 Bibliographic coupling of documents

The articles' bibliographic coupling of documents and a colour-coded cluster indicator are shown in Fig. 5. The amount of citations for each article is represented by the size of the nodes in Fig. 5. Additionally, the network's distance or proximity between studies indicates how closely the nodes and publications are related bibliographically. For instance, the proximity of the two articles means that they share a large number of references (Niknejad et al., 2021; Marchiori and Franco, 2019). The articles with a minimum of five citations were only considered in this study. Out of the 1013 documents, 472 related articles met the criteria. All of the publications' total link strengths and citation counts were calculated using the VOSviewer software, and the articles with the highest total link strengths were selected. The publication with the most citations, as shown in Fig. 5, was See-To E.W.K., (2014), with 346 citations and 47 total link strengths.

Fig. 6 Bibliographic coupling of countries

The bibliographic coupling of countries is depicted visually in Fig. 6, where each node denotes a country and its size denotes the number of publications in that country. The United States of America, China, South Korea, India, Japan and the Russian Federation are the top research-producing nations in the area of public relations in Asia which complements Fig. 2. The next analysis created by the VOSviewer software uses co-occurrence of the author's keywords to fully comprehend the top search terms for public relations

research in Asia during the present study period (Niknejad et al., 2021).

Fig. 7 Co-occurrence of authors' keywords

Fig.7 displays an analysis created by the VOSviewer programme, which was a method of thoroughly comprehending the most popular keywords for public relations at the time this study was being conducted and looks at the co-occurrence of the author's keywords. As shown in Fig. 7, public relations, social media, interprofessional education, customer relationship management, communication, interprofessional collaboration, and corporate social responsibility are leading in the keywords used most frequently.

This study used the R package bibliometrix to analyse the author keywords using Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA). The graphical analysis of categorical data could be conducted using the data analysis method known as MCA (Niknejad et al., 2021; Aria and Cuccurullo, 2017). The current study chose MCA since it can assist in identifying the topic organisation among a collection of authors' keywords. A category depiction of how frequently used keywords are applied together can be made using the MCA technique, where the keywords are clustered based on their proximity (Niknejad et al.,

2021; Demiroz and Haase, 2019). For instance, if two different keywords (e.g., public relations and human) are used simultaneously in multiple articles, these keywords can be clustered together (Niknejad et al., 2021; Aria and Cuccurullo, 2017).

Fig. 8 Conceptual map of author's keywords in publications related to public relations

Fig. 8 displays the conceptual organisation of the authors' keywords with respect to the publications on public relations research in Asia. The articles included in the analysis are shown to be divided into two major clusters in this figure, which illustrate the intellectual hierarchy of public relations research studies in Asia.

Fig. 9 Network view map generated by VOSviewer

Fig. 9 shows a network view map of the terms that were taken from article titles and abstracts. The obtained words are identified by labels, as seen in the network map. In some cases, the labels are not displayed to prevent circle overlap. The circle's size depends on how often an item appears. The relationships between the phrases are defined by the lines, while the colour reflects the cluster to which the terms belong. The separation between the objects shows how strong the connections are. For instance, terms that are closer to one another have stronger links than terms that are more apart (Niknejad et al., 2021; Eck and Waltman, 2019). As shown in Fig. 9, the most commonly-occurring terms (large circles) are public relations, interprofessional relations, humans, organisation and management, article, health personnel attitude, and psychology. The VOSviewer software classified the most frequently used terms into four clusters by the bibliometric mapping. The red-coloured cluster formed a larger group compared to the other colours, i.e. blue, green and yellow. The red cluster contains the terms focused on public relations with connections to strategic communication and social media platforms such as Facebook and Twitter apart from others. The blue cluster consists of terms focused on interprofessional relations relating to health and health personal attitudes to patients and the patient care team framework concentrated in Hong Kong. The green cluster too is focused on terms such as human and is

interconnected with terms such as organisation and management, disaster management, inter-institutional relations, social behaviour, cultural factors, concentrated in Japan. The aspect of stakeholders is also present in this cluster. The yellow cluster has a strong link with the blue cluster. Both clusters share similar terms relating to the healthcare industry, with words such as psychology, nursing education etc. Some keywords in this cluster consist of words such as psychology, middle-aged, preceptorship, mentor, nursing education, medical school, and education faculty. The purple colour is spread across and keywords such as communication, simulation, young adult etc. are found in this cluster.

4. Discussion

Public relation indicates how a person, company and its brand is being felt and seen by others. Public Relations for corporations, notable publicly traded companies focused on maintaining a positive corporate image with all its stakeholders, i.e media, investors, employees, customers etc. This field is emerging and research on public relations started in the year 1905 according to the Scopus-indexed database with 22 publications, the next publication was in 1930 after a gap of 25 years. The research trend on public relations – shows that the publications were oscillating till 1962 with few publications seen in post the 1930s. Surprisingly in the post 1962 sudden rise in the publication was witnessed. In the recent past, the field of public relations has attracted the much wider attention of researchers from across the world. The field has been redefined in multiple ways – from branding to social media management to influencer and media relations. Lately, public relations has evolved to be one of the popular disciplines because of the ongoing advances in both society and technology. This could be one of the possible reasons for the increase in publications of research work on public relations. In the year 2015, most publications with 3085 documents were witnessed. The present study is confined to the analysis of the publication in select countries of Asia during 2013-2022. More than 1013 articles were published during these years. Out of that, around 187

articles are single-authored and 826 articles are multi-authored. The average citation per article is 11.36. Around 3.23 % of the article is co-authored per document. In this process, we found that there are 2776 authors who have published 1013 articles. Most articles were published by the United States (320 articles) followed by China (310) and South Korea (198). The top cited journals from the reference list include an article titled “Value co-creation and purchase intention in social network sites: The role of electronic Word-of-Mouth and trust - A theoretical analysis” by See-To E.W.K. et al. had the highest citation of 246 and it was published on 2014. This study examines how electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM) influences purchase intention in Social networking sites using the theories of trust and value co-creation Social Networking sites (SNSs). Consistent increase in the global user of social media has widened the scope of public relations as well. From connecting friends and filling spare time now Social media is being used to sell the product and election campaigning. Perhaps, this could be one of the reasons for the article to have a wider readership.

Subsequently, the article titled “Antecedents and consequences of mobile phone usability: linking simplicity and interactivity to satisfaction, trust, and brand loyalty” by Lee D, Moons et. published in 2015 received the second highest citation, that is 236 citations. Scholars through this article studied the simplicity and interactivity as key determinants of the usability of mobile phones and their user interface using the questionnaire method. In the recent past, design and user-friendly mobile phones are changing the way we use digital tools for fulfilling various demands. The user interface plays a key role in determining the purchase behaviour of the customer.

The third most cited article is titled as “Factors influencing the use of social media by SMEs and its performance outcomes” by Ainin S. et. al. (2015) with 204 citations published. This article has investigated the factors that influence Facebook usage among small and medium enterprises (SMEs). Additionally, it investigates how Facebook usage affects SMEs' financial and non-financial

performance. This study helped to clarify the benefits and true significance of Facebook. The outcomes would encourage and direct businesses in using Facebook for commercial purposes. Moreover, the article makes a number of theoretical and applied contributions.

In the top 20 cited articles list, the most number of articles are dealing with social media and its usage in the field of public relations. The research work produced by Ainin S. et.al. (2015), Tajudeen F.P. et al. (2018), Hong, H (2013), Dhanesh G. S. (2019), Himelboim I. (2014) emphasised the various implications of social media. As discussed, the field of public relations is an emerging discipline and is considered to be adapting to the ever-changing society and advancement of technology. This certainly shows the importance of social media in the field of public relations. In addition to the topic of social media other topics such as employee and employer relationships along with employee and organisation relationships Kang M et al (2017) were prominently discussed topics. Other works such as Kang M et al. (2017) dealt with mediation between employee – organisation relations. In the same line another article Lian H et al. also dealt with the reciprocal relationship between abusing supervision and organisational deviance and Luo et al (2014) studied the role of firm employees and firm customer relationships. Literature on public relations in the top 20 cited articles mainly focused on Social networks and social media, employee and employer relations, Corporate Social Responsibility and Supply Chain management. This discussion on analysis of publications on public relations certainly throws light upon major emerging fields in the domain of public relations. As this discipline is evolving and it is expected to grow and influence many walks of human life and society as a whole.

5. Conclusion

This study presents the results of a bibliometric analysis of 1013 articles on public relations written between 2013 and 2022. The current investigation was conducted using the VoS viewer application and the R package bibliometrix. The findings

demonstrated that the researchers have been devoting more attention to the study of the concept of public relations, particularly in the year 2019 (134 docs) followed by 2022 (121 docs). The results also revealed that the USA, China, and South Korea are the top three countries for publishing articles on public relations.

The network view map generated using the VoS viewer indicated that studies on public relations were roughly divided into three major clusters and a few very smaller clusters. The red, blue, and green clusters formed larger groupings than the sky blue, and purple clusters. The term in the red cluster covers issues like public relations, sales, Artificial Intelligence (AI), marketing, advertising, media, democracy, government, twitter, Facebook, strategic communication, dialogue, culture, trust are more concentrated in Israel, Korea, Vietnam, Thailand and Russia.

The blue colour cluster formed the larger group but was relatively small compared to the red. The terms in the blue colour consist of keywords such as interprofessional relations, article, student, learning controlled study, cooperation, education health, occupation, teamwork, and patient care conceptual framework concentrated in Hong Kong. The green colour covers the keyword such as human, interview, social behaviour, organisation, politics, law, organisation and management, inter-institutional relations, social behaviour, cultural factor, faculty, publications concentrated Japan. The yellow colour cluster consists of keywords such as psychology, middle-aged, preceptorship, mentor, nursing education, medical school, and education faculty. The purple colour spread across the keywords such as communication, simulation, young adult etc.

The study has few limitations despite many scientific achievements. The data for the study has been retrieved from Scopus-indexed databases over other databases such as Web of Science, Pub med etc. This is one of the main limitations of the study. The Scopus database collects data using a full counting process. Due to this, papers with numerous

co-authors usually have more analytical relevance than those with just one author. This study also included fractional counting to mapping analysis utilising the VOSviewer programme to address this problem. Co-citation, bibliographic coupling, and the co-occurrence of author keywords were all considered in the analysis. Similar findings were obtained using complete and fractional counting. The study's conclusions can therefore be trusted because there is no discernible difference between the two counting techniques. The study is delimited to 10 years (2013-2022) although the study on public relations started in 1905. Numerous articles have been published till now. To provide an updated overview of the analysis of publications related to public relations to researchers, the study has been carried out for a period of 10 years. The findings of the study demonstrate that most of the publications in the field of public relations were related to social media, employee and employer relations, corporal social responsibility and supply chain management. There is no doubt that the discipline of public relations is an evolving discipline and the publications on the discipline have seen tremendous growth in the past few decades. As a result, it is advised that this research be carried out again in the upcoming years.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

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